

To Carbonate or not to Carbonate? An experimental Study on Synthetic and Industrial Recycled Cement Paste

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Abstract. Mineral carbonation has gained attention as a carbon utilization strategy, offering a way to permanently sequester CO₂ through its reaction with materials bearing metal oxides, such as calcium and magnesium, forming stable carbonates. Within the field of cement production, Recycled Cement Paste (RCP) offers a carbon utilization pathway, where the carbonated RCP (cRCP) can be used as a Supplementary Cementitious Material (SCM) in composite cements. The latter is vastly reported through studies conducted on synthetic Hydrated Cement Paste (HCP). To broaden the scope of cRCP use in cement, this study investigates and industrially-sourced RCP (RCP-i), while utilizing a laboratory-synthesized samples of HCP as a reference. Both materials undergo mineral carbonation at ambient temperature under wet conditions. Thermogravimetry and LECO analyses were used to measure carbonation uptake, and the R3 test to assess the pozzolanic reactivity of the carbonated products. Also, blended cement pastes were prepared with Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) and HCP or RCP-i (before and after carbonation) at a 20% replacement by weight of OPC — to assess the impact on hydration characteristics using isothermal calorimetry. For the tested materials, results show that a) the carbonated variants perform similarly to their uncarbonated counterparts as cement replacements, and b) the actual CO₂ uptake of the RCP-i is less than one-third of that of the synthetic HCP. For this particular RCP-i, the conclusion seems to be not to carbonate.

Keywords: Mineral Carbonation, Recycled Cement Paste, SCMs.

1 Introduction

The depletion of natural resources, the magnitude of volumes of global construction and demolition waste (CDW) generation, and high levels of emissions that accompany cement production (8% of anthropogenic carbon emissions) has led to Carbonated Recycled Cement Paste (cRCP) increasingly being explored as a potential new Supplementary Cementitious Material (SCM), straddling potential use-cases in waste recycling for the circular economy and in Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS).

Mineral carbonation is a method by which CO₂ can be trapped within calcium- and magnesium-rich minerals in stable carbonate forms that do not contribute to the

39 greenhouse effect [1-3]. The main products formed after the mineral carbonation of an
 40 end-of-life cement paste are calcium carbonate, produced through the reaction of port-
 41 landite with carbon dioxide, and an amorphous silica-alumina gel, which results from
 42 the de-calcification of calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) [3-5]. This silica-alumina gel
 43 is highly reactive, with researchers reporting that it completes nearly 90% of its reaction
 44 within the first seven days, a rate much faster than other SCMs currently in use [3,7].

45 About 6.0 Gt/y of end-of-life concrete and mortar are produced globally per year, of
 46 which ca. 20% comprises end-of-life cement paste. It has been estimated that the pro-
 47 duction of cRCP would be 2 to 5 times cheaper than CO₂ capture and storage as a
 48 decarbonization strategy for the construction industry [6].

49 However, a majority of existing studies exploring the mechanism and performance
 50 of cRCP have been conducted on hydrated cement paste (HCP) that was cast and hy-
 51 drated in laboratory conditions, with few exceptions such as [5]. Industrially processed
 52 RCP is more heterogenous, may have already been subjected to natural carbonation,
 53 and contains a larger non-reactive component, hampering its actual carbonation uptake
 54 and increase in pozzolanic reactivity. Given that industrial products incorporating RCP
 55 already exist (conforming to EN197-5), there is a consideration to be made: to car-
 56 bonate or not to carbonate?

57 In this study, HCP and RCP are carbonated and compared on the basis of their CO₂
 58 uptake as well as to their uncarbonated counterparts in terms of pozzolanic reactivity
 59 to determine if the obtained improvement would justify the cost of carbonation.

60 2 Materials

61 The materials used in this study were hydrated cement paste (HCP) synthesized in the
 62 laboratory and recycled cement paste (RCP-i) of industrial origin. Table 1 provides
 63 their particle size distribution and specific surface area (SSA).

64 The HCP was prepared using an industrial CEM I 52.5N paste casted at a water/ce-
 65 ment (w/c) ratio of 0.48. Post-curing under sealed conditions, the paste samples were
 66 sealed and allowed to hydrate for 24 months to ensure a high degree of hydration and
 67 prevent carbonation. The sample was then ground using a disk mill and passed through
 68 a 100 µm sieve and stored in air-tight jars.

69 The RCP-i derives from an industrial recycling process of end-of-life concrete. The
 70 old mortar is separated from the aggregates, and this powder is then subjected to addi-
 71 tional enrichment forms to obtain the RCP-i.

72 *Table 1. Physical Characteristics of HCP and RCP-i before and after carbonation.*

Properties	HCP	RCP-i	cHCP	cRCP-i
D10 (µm)	4.4	5.8	6.6	5.2
D50 (µm)	11.5	11.8	12.9	10.2
D90 (µm)	72.1	23.2	28.0	19.4
SSA (m ² /g)	17.5	8.7	33.1	26.8

73 For isothermal calorimetry measurements, the primary reference paste was anordi-
 74 nary Portland Cement (OPC), i.e. a CEM I 42.5N (EN 197-1). Additionally, a CEM

75 II/C-M (F-T) 42.5 N (EN 197-5) and a blend of CEM I 42.5N with 20% limestone were
 76 included as reference materials. Since the CEM II/C-M (F-T) 42.5 N already incorpo-
 77 rates 20% recycled material, the other materials used in this study were also substituted
 78 at the same 20% ratio to maintain consistency. The paste compositions used in the iso-
 79 thermal calorimetry measurements are given in Table 2.

80 Additionally, quartz was added in two proportions to the cHCP to mimic the com-
 81 position of cRCP-i. The intent here is to assess the contribution of cHCP in the heat of
 82 hydration upon different dilution factors. Specifically, a sample with a 20% substitution
 83 of quartz was added following an earlier HCP study [9], and a 40% substitution of
 84 quartz was added to form a better approximation to the RCP-i unreactive fraction.

85 *Table 2. Paste Compositions Used for Isothermal Calorimetry, by mass percentage.*

Sample	Cement type	Cement	LS	HCP	RCP-i	cHCP	cRCP-i	Quartz
CEM-II	CEM II 42.5	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
CEM-I		100	0	0	0	0	0	0
LS-20		80	20	0	0	0	0	0
RCP-20		80	0	0	20	0	0	0
HCP-12-Q-8	CEM I 42.5	80	0	12	0	0	0	8
cRCP-20		80	0	0	0	0	20	0
cHCP-12-Q-8		80	0	0	0	12	0	8
cHCP-16-Q-4		80	0	0	0	16	0	4

86 **3 Methods**

87 **3.1 Carbonation Reactor**

88 Wet enforced carbonation was selected as the method of mineral carbonation due to its
 89 ability to operate under ambient temperature and pressure conditions [3]. As this study
 90 was focused solely on comparing uncarbonated and carbonated material, the specifics
 91 of the carbonation process, such as kinetics of reaction, are not included in its scope.

92 Pastes carbonation was conducted in a lab-scale reactor, see Figure 1. Pure CO₂ gas
 93 was bubbled directly into an aqueous suspension comprising 30 g of crushed paste dis-
 94 persed in 150 g of deionized water. Temperature and pH measurements were taken at
 95 regular intervals of 5 minutes. The gas flow was monitored using a flowmeter to ensure
 96 a constant flow rate of 2.0 L/min over the course of the experiment. Suspension homo-
 97 geneity was maintained using a magnetic stirrer running at 700 rpm.

98 The materials were carbonated for 60 minutes. The pH values for the suspensions
 99 were in the range of 12.0 - 13.5 before the commencement of carbonation and would
 100 stabilize around 6.2 - 6.4 by the end of the experiment. The carbonated material was
 101 then dried in a 105°C oven and ground to pass through a 100 µm sieve for analysis.

Figure 1. Schematic of the Lab-Scale Carbonation Reactor

102
103

104 3.2 Experimental Techniques

105 The uncarbonated and carbonated materials are compared based on composition,
106 carbonation uptake, and influence on cement paste hydration.

107 For the calculation of carbonation uptake, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and
108 carbon content analysis were performed. Namely, TGA was conducted using a TA In-
109 strument TGA Q50 in the temperature range of 30-1000^o C, with the carbon dioxide
110 uptake measured to be the difference in mass loss between uncarbonated and car-
111 bonated material in the temperature range of 500-900^o C.

112 In addition, a LECO® CS-844 device was used to measure the amount of carbon in
113 a sample, using Synthetic Carbon 502-632 as the Standard Reference Material (SRM).
114 The difference between the carbon content in the samples before and after carbonation
115 was used to calculate the carbon dioxide uptake.

116 The BET Specific Surface Area (SSA_{BET}) was determined by the nitrogen adsorption
117 technique (Micromeritics Tristar II 3020), after degassing at 40°C for 16 h under N₂
118 flow. The PSD was measured through laser diffractometry using a HORIBA LA 950
119 from Retsch Technology. The elemental composition was measured using X-ray Flu-
120 rescence (XRF) and analyzed using the Spectra^{plus} software, v.6.61 from Bruker.

121 For the influence on cement paste hydration, R3 (ASTM C1897-20) and isothermal
122 calorimetry test were conducted by a TAMair and iCal 8000 calorimeter, respectively.
123 For isothermal calorimeter, measurements were carried out at 23°C to compare the per-
124 formance of the materials when used as cement substituents at a 20% substitution level.

125 4 Results and Discussion

126 4.1 CO₂ Uptake

127 The elemental composition of the uncarbonated pastes are given in Table 3.

128 Equation 1 presents a modified version of the Steinoor formula [11] that was used
129 to calculate the theoretical maximum uptake of carbon dioxide, also known as the car-
130 bonation potential, denoted here as P.

131
$$P = 0.785[(\%CaO) - 0.56(\%CaCO_3) - 0.7(\%SO_3)] + 1.091(\%MgO), \quad (1)$$

132 where $CaCO_3$ is obtained from TGA results by calculating the mass loss between 600
 133 and 850°C. Based on this formula, the theoretical maximum carbonation uptake is cal-
 134 culated for the materials, while the actual CO_2 uptake was calculated experimentally in
 135 two ways: a) from the mass loss between 500 and 900°C (a broader range to account
 136 for a wider variety of carbonates) as detected through TGA, and b) from the change in
 137 carbon content as detected by the LECO analyzer.

138 *Table 3. Elemental Composition of HCP and RCP-i from XRF, by percentage of mass*

Component	HCP (%)	RCP-i (%)
LOI (975°C)	27.66	14.61
SiO ₂	14.68	46.50
CaO	46.38	24.86
Al ₂ O ₃	3.08	5.32
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.29	2.92
SO ₃	2.97	1.67
MgO	0.59	1.47
TiO ₂	0.17	0.40
Na ₂ O	0.21	0.39
K ₂ O	0.43	1.32
P ₂ O ₅	0.24	0.16

139 The TGA results are presented in Figure 2. The expected peaks include one around
 140 450°C that registers as a consequence of the dehydroxylation of portlandite, and another
 141 between 500 to 900°C that forms because of the decarbonation of present carbonates,
 142 when they decompose into oxides and carbon dioxide.

143 From Figure 2 it is observed that the HCP has a discernible dehydroxylation peak
 144 while the RCP-i has none. Also, the RCP-i has a decarbonation peak, either due to the
 145 natural carbonation it has already undergone or due to remnants of carbonate-contain-
 146 ing aggregates. The cHCP and cRCP-i have clear decarbonation peaks, evidencing CO_2
 147 uptake – where cHCP has sequestered more CO_2 than cRCP-i.

148
149

Figure 2. Mass loss rate (dTG), normalized by mass of oven-dry material at 105°C

150 The experimentally calculated CO_2 uptake values are given in Table 4, normalized both
151 by the weight of the oven-dry material at 105°C for 12 hours and LOI-free material.
152 Using these values, the carbonation uptake (U) and degree (α) can be computed by Eqs.
153 2 and 3. Note that U provides the actual amount of carbon dioxide fixed by the material
154 in % (normalized to original mass including the LOI), and α provides the progress of
155 CO_2 uptake in relation to the theoretical value (see Equation 1). The comparison between
156 the theoretical potential and actual carbonation uptake of the materials is given
157 in Table 5.

$$158 \quad U = \frac{\text{CO}_2\%_{\text{carbonated(LOI-free)}} - \text{CO}_2\%_{\text{uncarbonated(LOI-free)}}}{100} \times (100 - \text{LOI}) \quad (2)$$

$$159 \quad \alpha = 100 \frac{U}{P} \quad (3)$$

160

Table 4. CO_2 content, before and after carbonation.

Material	CO_2 (% by mass of oven-dry material at 105°C)		CO_2 (% normalized LOI-free)	
	TGA	LECO	TGA	LECO
HCP	4.29	2.58	5.21	3.13
cHCP	28.76	26.99	38.72	36.43
RCP-i	6.02	7.27	6.86	8.30
cRCP-i	12.62	14.95	14.87	16.82

161

Table 5. Theoretical vs. Experimental comparison of CO_2 uptake

Material	P (%)	U (%)		α (%)	
		TGA	LECO	TGA	LECO
HCP	32.6	24.2	24.1	74.2	73.9
RCP-i	15.4	6.8	7.3	44.1	47.4

162 The HCP demonstrated a higher ability to capture CO₂ in comparison to RCP-i. Even
163 when the CO₂ uptake of the HCP was diluted down to 60% to account for the presence
164 of non-reactive material, it still captured over twice as much CO₂ as the RCP-i.

165 Multiple carbonation iterations were run with modifications made to the dilution ra-
166 tio, duration of carbonation, and flow rate of carbon dioxide to observe any potential
167 changes to the carbonation uptake. None have yielded any tangible improvements,
168 which suggests that these limitations may be a consequence of the composition of the
169 material rather than the specifics of the carbonation process. Let it be noted that an in-
170 depth investigation on process parameters is beyond the scope of this work.

171 **4.2 Reactivity as an SCM**

172 Analysis of the isothermal calorimetric data normalized by weight of binder revealed
173 that carbonated materials showed a higher rate of heat release during the initial disso-
174 lution period, see Figure 3(a). There did not seem to be a pattern to the modification of
175 the shape of the heat release curve. After 24 hours, the cRCP-20 sample released an
176 average of 7.8% more heat, compared to the references and uncarbonated samples,
177 while the cHCP-12-Q-8 and cHCP-16-Q-4 released an average of 6.1% and 12.8%
178 more heat respectively. However, CEM-I overtook all the other pastes by the end of 48
179 hours, releasing an average of 11.9% more heat than other samples by the end of three
180 days.

181 Upon reaching the 7-day benchmark, the cumulative heat released by all pastes are
182 within a standard deviation of 5%, rendering the difference statistically insignificant,
183 as seen in Figure 4. While the other materials displayed performance comparable to the
184 references, they did not exhibit any notable improvement or advantage over the refer-
185 ence formulations.

Figure 3. Hydration heat rate curves (a) initial dissolution (b) 3-day

Figure 4. Cumulative heat release over 7 days.

192 The impact on the heat release could partially be due to a combination of filler and
 193 nucleation effects, resulting from a decrease in particle size and increase in SSA (see
 194 Table 1). The contribution from the silica-alumina gel is unknown as the amount of gel
 195 formed was not quantified. However, the R3 test results, given in Table 6, indicate that
 196 the amount of heat released places both the uncarbonated as well as the carbonated
 197 materials in the range of low pozzolanic reactivity.

198 The R3 results confirmed that carbonation can cause an increase in pozzolanic reactivity,
 199 though the discrepancy between HCP and RCP-i exists here as well, with cHCP
 200 exhibiting an improvement of about 54% over HCP, while cRCP only improves by
 201 around 19% compared to RCP-i, a little over one-third compared to the cHCP. However,
 202 when normalized against the carbonation uptake percentage, as shown in Table 6,
 203 the improvement in pozzolanic reactivity was greater in RCP-i than in HCP. Understanding
 204 this difference may require additional characterization and studies on the individual
 205 products of carbonation, which is not included in this paper.

206 It is important to note that lack of clarity on whether the R3 test can accurately and
 207 completely capture the behavior of RCP has to be considered, since the standardization
 208 of test methods for chemically activated materials, especially carbonated materials, has
 209 not been well established yet.

210

Table 6. R3 test results.

Property	HCP	cHCP		RCP-i	cRCP-i	
		TGA	LECO		TGA	LECO
7-day Heat Release (J/g of SCM)	84	129		99	118	
Increase in Heat (normalized by carbonation uptake) (J/g/%)		1.9	1.9		2.8	2.6
Increase in Heat (normalized by carbonation uptake) (%/%)		2.3	2.3		2.8	2.6

211 5 Conclusions

212 In this study, synthetic HCP and industrial RCP were evaluated and compared in terms
 213 of their CO₂ sequestration capacity and influence on hydration characteristics when
 214 subjected to wet enforced carbonation. The experimental findings indicate that both
 215 uncarbonated and carbonated materials exhibited comparable hydration performance
 216 over the first seven days when used at a 20% mass replacement of OPC. There were no
 217 statistically significant differences observed in the total heat release, though a slight
 218 improvement was observed with the pastes incorporating carbonated substitutions in
 219 the first 24 hours. Though the pozzolanic reactivity fell within the low-reactivity range
 220 in the R3 test, an improvement was observed after the material underwent carbonation.

221 A marked disparity was revealed in their carbonation behavior. The RCP-i demon-
222 strated a limited carbonation uptake under conditions where the synthetic counterpart
223 could bind significantly higher amounts of CO₂, reaching a higher carbonation degree
224 as well. Even when the capacity of synthetic material was diluted to account for the
225 non-reactive fraction, it was still able to bind nearly double the amount of CO₂ as com-
226 pared to the RCP-i. There appear to be compositional factors limiting the carbonation
227 uptake of RCP-i that require further investigation.

228 Altogether, these results highlight a critical gap between laboratory-scale investiga-
229 tions utilizing synthetic materials and the practical performance of industrial products
230 subjected to enforced carbonation. Further research is necessary to investigate the un-
231 derlying inhibiting carbonation of industrial RCP to bridge this gap. Given the hetero-
232 geneity of industrial RCP, low binding capacity, and lack of material on a large scale,
233 alternative processing approaches or simply using the uncarbonated material may be
234 recommended as they may be more effective methods to use the material.

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